

DELEGATION AND MOTIVATION AS A FUNCTION OF MANAGEMENT IN STATE STRUCTURES.

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Annotation: The article deals with the process of delegation of authority as a function of management in state structures, its advantages and disadvantages are described.

Key words: delegation, employees, management, motivation, government organizations, government agencies.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается процесс делегирования полномочий как функция управления в государственных структурах, описываются его преимущества и недостатки.

Ключевые слова: делегирование, сотрудники, управление, мотивация, государственные организации, государственные учреждения.

Relations within the organization are carried out through the existence of a specific organizational structure, a specially authorized sub organization, the exercise of authority and the delegation of responsibility, as defined in the regulatory documents of the organization itself.

Delegation is a function of the leadership of an organization. Motivation provides a qualitative improvement in the performance of tasks delegated within the framework of authority, with the help of various incentives.

Delegation is responsible for the managerial aspect, and motivation characterizes the psychological aspect of relationships for the implementation of high quality and productive results. Since delegated tasks are personal in nature, the psychological component is of great importance. Innovative activity requires the creation of an environment conducive to high-quality teamwork. When organizing teamwork, managers need to take into account the standard of living of their subordinates, their interests, environment, abilities and competencies. The problem of building relationships between top management and subordinates never becomes obsolete, and today it is of particular relevance. In other words, the "golden rule" that is the essence of a good manager in a public organization is to get certain results by distributing them among subordinates, which remains unchanged when it comes to management. Effective management depends on the ability to properly distribute their powers. The overall

management function reflects the content of the main stages of the organization's management process at all hierarchical levels. Delegation means the organization of such a scenario, in which each subordinate performs his duties with enthusiasm, responsibility, creativity and maximum dedication within the framework of delegated authority. However, self-realization is not inferior to working in a team environment.

The purpose of this management function is to delegate authority and responsibility to staff in such a way that the best results are achieved in the shortest possible time and at the lowest cost.

The advantages of this type of control are the following:

1. A creative atmosphere is achieved in the team.
2. The management team becomes more responsive and spends less time getting instructions for assigned work.
3. A team is being formed to improve work efficiency.
4. The psychological climate is improving and a personnel reserve is being formed.
5. Increased staff motivation.
6. A group is being formed that can act independently and solve problematic, non-standard issues.

However, in order to achieve the above, it is necessary to build the right work scenario.

The socio-psychological climate in public institutions largely depends on the leadership style that prevails in this sector. Leadership style is usually understood as the type and manner of exercising managerial functions that managers express in their relationships with subordinates.

Informal leadership styles arise when it is impossible or impractical for management to fully regulate the management function. The informal leadership style provides leaders with greater freedom, but requires more effort, authority and professional skills from them. Formal and informal management styles do not occur in pure practice in the management sector. Vertical relationships and communications attempt to demonstrate formal control, while horizontal communications occur without strict regulation. Signs of target orientation, field of activity and forms of organization of leadership are interconnected and can form the most effective system of relationships and a comfortable psychological climate in creative teams. Advanced forms of leadership in innovation management are increasingly acquiring signs of a democratic style. In the field of innovation, two styles are possible: the first is task-oriented; the second is

employee-oriented. The first style ensures the achievement of goals through planning and control of management actions; the second one uses methods such as delegation, motivation, and the establishment of creative relationships in a team [1].

Delegation of authority can be done in two ways. First, the delegation of authority to a specific person with an indication of job responsibilities. Secondly, the delegation of authority to specific positions, i.e. distribution of powers through the formation of the organizational structure of management. Delegation results are influenced by external and internal factors and parameters of delegation.

In a market economy, it is necessary to be prepared for crises at any time, as they often occur and cause significant changes in work processes. Therefore, during a crisis, the time for making decisions decreases, there is a need to quickly adjust to external conditions and take measures to eliminate problems and achieve the goal. A clear sequence is required from all employees, and the role of managers at all levels is increasing. Thus, the requirements for completing tasks are changing. As a result, responsibility is increased both for the results of the work of employees and for the results of the work of the management itself. The psychological climate worsens, which leads to a decrease in the activity of HR, anxiety about the implementation of complex projects, individualism and conflicts between employees. The requirements for completing tasks are growing, and the level of remuneration, as a rule, remains the same. Since the fate of an organization may depend on the actions of individual employees, it is often necessary to look for personnel who are ready to take full responsibility and implement their ideas [2].

Possible forms of delegation: a) providing greater freedom of action, b) "horizontal" rotation, c) involving subordinates in the process of making managerial decisions, d) encouraging initiative.

The conditions for successful delegation of authority are trust in employees, knowledge, and experience and business skills in delegating authority, setting specific goals and simultaneously training employees.

Thus, the implementation of the strategy depends on the leadership style of the state body and the competence of its employees. Achieving the goals of the state organization is a long process, which is influenced by external and internal conditions. When choosing a management strategy, it is necessary to analyze the existing environment of the relevant organization.

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